

Epibionts Assemblage of Macroalgae in Mangroves Area at Bhavnagar District, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:- Mangroves are a multifunctional and unique component of marine ecosystem as it provide nursery to marine animal, protection from high waves, floods, cyclone, as store blue carbon. Mangrove forest support diversified macroalgae in their community. Typically mangrove occurs near shoreline, in intertidal zone of coast, deltas, estuaries, lagoons and muddy flats. This study conducted to assess the habitat characteristics of mangrove macroalgae at Gopnath coast Bhavnagar District, Gujarat, India. Coast of Gopnath contains 1 true mangrove species *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh. One group of macroalgae were recorded to be growing on mangrove root and mangrove field, total 4 species of green algae recorded during this study.

Keywords:- Macroalgae, Mangroves, Habitat characteristic, Diversity

I. INTRODUCTION

Mangroves are a multifunctional and unique component of marine ecosystem grow in tropical and subtropical coast (Hoque et al., 2015) and as it provides nursery to marine animal, protection from high waves, floods, cyclone, as store blue carbon. Mangrove forest support divers' macroalgae in their community. Mangrove's dead branches, prop roots, pneumatophores, branches and roots prop up distinct macroalgal assemblages as epibionts in the intertidal zone. (Dawes et al., 1999; Zhang et al., 2014).

This marine macroalgae and mangroves association provide carbon to the primary consumers in the aquatic food web (Koch & Madden, 2001) making them a considerable contributor in the marine ecosystems (Stoner & Zimmerman, 1988). Root structure of mangrove provides hard substrate for some variety of marine flora and fauna.

The height of pneumatophores, surface texture, distance of pneumatophores, and canopy of mangroves affects the distribution of macroalgae in mangroves area. Environmental parameter such as temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, pH etc. have been considered to be controlling factor that influence the presence and absent of macro marine algae in mangrove habitat (Fernandes & Aives 2011).

II. OBJECTIVE OF RESEARCH WORK

The main purpose of this study is to investigate role of marine algae and mangrove species to maintain marine environment, coastal area, marine faunal diversity, coastal economy. As the marine algae and mangroves are primary producer of ecosystem that maintain the food chain and provide nursery to marine fauna. This study will help to know the current status of marine diversity. This data are useful for the future reference in field of climate change effect, effect of sea level rise, environmental engineering, coastal engineering, marine engineering to making strategies for conservation and protection.

III. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A. Study Site

Study was carried out at Gopnath Coast (21°12'31"N 72°6'34"E) located in Bhavnagar District, Gujarat, India. The intertidal area was rocky to muddy. Mangrove habitat only present in muddy and sandy region at Gopnath coast. *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh is a single mangrove species present at Gopnath coast.

Fig 1: Map of Gopnath coast, Bhavnagar, Gujarat, India.

B. Sample Collection

Sample was collected seasonally (summer, monsoon, post monsoon, winter) in year of 2021 to 2022. Macroalgal data collected randomly in every season by using 1 m² quadrat. Pneumatophores of mangrove covered with macroalgae were collected for the identification purpose. Length of pneumatophores measure by using measuring tap, sharp blade and knife used to collect pneumatophores from the

field during low tide, physicochemical parameter of seawater such as Temperature, pH, Total Dissolved Solids, Electrical Conductivity, Salt Concentration recorded during all four seasons by using multi-parameter kit.

C. Statistical Analysis

The frequency (F) for each algal species were calculated as the number of pneumatophores on which that species was detected ($\sum N$) and total number of pneumatophores (N) studied.

$$\text{Frequency} = \sum N / N \text{ (Phillips et al., 1996)}$$

Abundance calculated by standard formula:

$$\frac{\text{Total number of individual species in all quadrats}}{\text{Total number of quadrats in which species occurs}}$$

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

➤ **Diversity of Mangrove:-**

Only single species of mangrove *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh observed during this investigation from the Gopnath beach. These white mangrove species will be found dominantly at study site from all quadrat in form of herb as well as in a form of shrub. Some plant present in muddy, sandy area and some also present on hard surface like rock. *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh bearing pneumatophores for breathing activity. pneumatophores present in much numbers while in hard surface area its present in less number.

Fig:2 Structure of *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh

➤ **Taxonomic Classification of *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh:-**

Domain: Eukaryota
 Kingdome: plantae
 Phylum: spermatophyte
 Subphylum: angiospermae
 Class: dicotyledonae
 Order: lamiales
 Family: acanthaceae
 Genus: *Avicennia* L.
 Species: *Avicennia marina* (Forssk.) Vierh.

➤ **Plant Characteristic:**

Plant contains pencil like pneumatophores pop up above ground with forming shallow underground roots network. Leaves simple, 3-6 cm long and 2- 3cm wide, opposite, elliptic, acute apex, glabrous and glaucous. Flower yellow, sessile in condensed terminal cyme.

Fig:3 flower(left) and fruit(right) structure of *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh

➤ **Phytosociological Analysis of Mangrove:-**

Table:1 phytosociological analysis of mangrove.

Species Name	<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forsk.) Vierh
Frequency	94%
Relative Frequency	100%
Abundance	4.02
Relative Abundance	100%
Density	3.78
Relative Density	100%
IVI	300

Field study and qualitative study shows single mangrove species *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh. in all sampling unit with 94% frequency, 4.02 (plants/450m²) abundance, 3.78 (plants/450m²) density, 300 important value index and with 100% relative abundance and relative density.

➤ **Diversity of Marine Macroalgae:-**

Total 4 varieties of macroalgae *Ulva prolifera*, *Ulva ovata*, *Ulva intestinalis* and *Ulva compress* recorded in this investigation. Investigated macroalgae belongs to same genus *Ulva*, family *Ulvaceae* and same division *Chlorophyta*. There is absence of red algae and brown algae.

1. *Ulva intestinalis* Linnaeus:

Thalli are simple and branching near base sometimes proliferous structure present, appear green to yellowish-green, 15-40 cm high, 0.5–1.0cm wide, solitary, comprised of several cylindrical, hollow, narrow tubular to flattened blades, with smooth or wrinkled surface, Margins entire or twisted to curly. Attachment by small disc-like holdfast on pneumatophores as well as on sand particles.

2. *Ulva ovata* Thivey et Visalakshmi ex Joshi et Krishnamurthy:

Thalli yellowish green, 0.3-2 cm wide and 0.5-4.0 cm long. Frond hollow, single, simple, flat, ovate. Attached with substrate by minute holdfast. It is endemic to Indian coast.

3. *Ulva prolifera* (Müller) J. Agardh:

Thallus tubulose, branched and filamentous. Thallus appear dark green, 10 to 13 cm long, profusely branched and attached by disk like hold fast with substratum.

4. *Ulva Compressa* (Linnaeus) Nees:

Thallus tubulose and compressed, plant yellowish green up to 11cm long, narrow, obtuse or round apices and stalk like base.

Fig:4 epibionts assemblage of macroalgae on pneumatophores of *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh; A. *Ulva prolifera*, B. *Ulva compressa*, C. *Ulva intestinalis*, D. *Ulva ovata*

Ulva ovata present in 3 seasons (Monsoon, Post monsoon and winter) with maximum frequency while *Ulva prolifera*, *Ulva intestinalis* and *Ulva compressa* present in post monsoon and winter season, while in summer season diversity were not observed.

The maximum abundance reported in winter season for *Ulva prolifera* and *Ulva ovata*. Table 2 shows The occurrence of macroalgae on pneumatophores is up to the 15 cm from the basal area. *Ulva prolifera*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *Ulva compressa* present on soil sediments only when it contain sand type particles.

Graph:1 Frequency of marine macroalgae assemblage with pneumatophores

Graph:2 Abundance of marine macroalgae assemblage with pneumatophores

The maximum abundance reported in winter season for *Ulva prolifera* and *Ulva ovata*. Table 2 shows The occurrence of macroalgae on pneumatophores is up to the 15 cm from the basal area. *Ulva prolifera*, *Ulva intestinalis*, *Ulva compress*

present on soil sediments only when it contain sand type particles.

➤ Physico-chemical parameter of seawater:-

Table:2 Substratum preference of marine macroalgae

Macroalgae	Pneumatophores		Soil Sediments	
	Basel area	Apex area	Sandy soil	Muddy soil
<i>Ulva prolifera</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Ulva ovata</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Ulva intestinalis</i>	+	-	+	-
<i>Ulva compress</i>	+	-	+	-

In summer season maximum reading recorded in temperature, Electrical conductivity and total dissolved solids. While minimum value recorded in winter season for temperature, electrical conductivity. Minimum value of pH,

Dissolved oxygen and Total dissolved solids, salt concentration recorded in monsoon and post monsoon.

Table:3 average data of physic-chemical parameter of seawater

Season	Tempera-ture °C	pH	EC (mS)	TDS (ppt)	SALT (ppt)	D.O.(mg/l)
Summer	33.2	8.1	49.7	31.7	21.3	6.70
Monsoon	31.9	7.90	45.9	30.2	22.9	3.64
Post monsoon	31.1	8.34	38.1	24	18.2	7.0
Winter	27.8	8.18	36.4	24.2	18.4	6.98

V. CONCLUSIONS

Investigation shows there is single species of mangrove *Avicennia marina* (Forsk.) Vierh. Was dominant and Presence-absences of macroalgal species is depend on morphological structure of pneumatophores as well as the seasonal changes that would affect the growth of macroalgal growth. Conservation and development of mangrove give chance to flourish more macroalgal diversity that increase the diversity of marine flora and fauna.

Pneumatophore of mangrove varies in height from 10 cm to 35 cm, macroalgae present on the basal area of pneumatophores near to soil sediments. *Ulva ovate*, *Ulva prolifera* and *Ulva compressa* present with 100% frequency in winter season. *Ulva ovate* (108.8), *Ulva prolifera* (93.8), *Ulva compressa*(85.8)and *Ulva intestinalis* (34.8)abundant in winter season.

Apart from contributing immensely in the primary trophic level in the marine ecosystem marine algae assist in harvesting excess carbon dioxide in the atmosphere and provide refuge for a diversity of organisms. Besides, the study also discussed some important hydrological factors that can influence the occurrence and abundance of mangrove macroalgae. References and literature on mangrove associated marine macroalgae in Bhavnagar district was not sufficient so, this investigation of epibionts assemblage of macro algae in mangroves area is very important in the area of Bhavnagar district, Gujarat, India. Presented data may prove useful in experimental design for future research aimed at investigating suitable macroalgal bio-indicator species from mangrove systems, detailed relationship between mangrove and marine algae.

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